

THE INFLUENCING FACTOR OF HANDLING RELATIONSHIP ABILITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENT IN INDONESIA; A PATH ANALYSIS

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Abstract

In this study, we look at the factors that influence handling relationships among university students in Indonesia. In this case, various emotional intelligence features were investigated, including emotion management, empathy, self-awareness, and motivation oneself. The participants were 288 Indonesian university students. Pearson correlation and path analysis were used to investigate the correlation and test the hypothesised model's direct and indirect effects. We discovered a substantial association between managing emotion, empathy, self-awareness, and motivation to handle relationships using pearson correlation. Furthermore, the hypothesised path model proved significant. We discovered a substantial direct effect of self-awareness, empathy, and managing emotion on the handling relationship by path analysis. We also discovered a significant indirect effect of motivation oneself on the handling relationship, which was mediated by managing emotion. We feel that the current study's findings broaden our understanding of the factors that influence university students' capacity to manage their relationships.

Keywords: Handling Relation, Emotional Intelligence Trait, University Students, Path Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Handling relationships is important for university students' academic lives. Handling relationships refers to students' ability to form positive interactions with their peers, instructors, and academic staff; inability to do so leads to stress and health issues (Yang et al., 2021). The importance of handling relationships among university students is grounded in the characteristic that humans are belong-making creatures, which means that humans

fundamentally need to belong to maintain enduring interpersonal attachment (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014). Fitzgerald and Konrad (2021) discovered in their research that students who struggle with relationships have higher levels of worry and tension, questioning their ability to deal with challenging areas of their lives and having difficulty achieving their goals. Students who are better at handling relationships, on the other hand, will experience less tension and worry. It is significant since, according to Gao et al. (2020), university students face higher stress and have more serious mental health problems than school students. Other than that, handling relationships also enhances the students social support from friends and family (Awang et al., 2014). It is because the ability to handle relationships creates humans who have social competence and wellbeing (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014). In regard to university life, university students should build positive relationships with peers and lecture. According to Capern and Hammond (2014), positive relationships between teacher and student have a significant impact on generating a suitable learning environment, which leads to a satisfying learning outcome. Positive relations between students and teachers are manifested through mutual acceptance, understanding, trust, cooperation, and warmth (Suryani, 2018). Therefore, it has been considered an important feature of the higher education learning environment (Tormey, 2021). It is also important for university students to handle relationships with peers. According to Maunder (2017), positive relationships among university students and peers could build social integration, which is an important factor in the success of the transition to university life. Based on the self-determination theory, peers are essential agents to fulfil students psychological needs, which affect their optimal performance and academic engagement (Ryan et al., 2019). It was also strengthened by Lan (2023), who stated that students who are well accepted or have good relationships with their peers tend to actively engage in academic activities.

Inability to handle relationships or build positive relationships among university students might cause stressful life and conflict. For many students, university might be a stressful life as they should negotiate with new communities and relationships (Alsubaie et al., 2019). According to Maunder (2017), university life could be a turbulent time since the students need to adjust to a new and unfamiliar environment. Failing to build positive relationships with new people might lead to conflict. According to Kiralp et al. (2009), the reason university students have personal conflict is the diversity in the relationships they have to deal with in order to get along with others. University students commonly leave their homes and meet with new people who have different subcultures and characteristics. Therefore, university students are facing a kind of interpersonal relationship that they are not familiar with, which is likely to increase stress in many ways and possibly increase interpersonal conflicts (Huang et al., 2016). This case may happen among university students in Indonesia since Indonesia is a multidimensional country with hundreds of cultures and religions (Ikhsan & Giwangsa, 2019). Furthermore, Nafi'a et al. (2022) stated that many educators in Indonesian universities have yet to perceive openness and respect for differences between minority groups and marginalised groups. This could lead to personal conflict between university students and other stakeholders. Ansyah et al. (2018), in their research, emphasise the urgency of quality relationships between students and teachers and students and peers in Indonesia. They stated that in Indonesia, we can easily understand

the poor relationship between students, teachers, and peers through the many violent cases that happen. Noer et al. (2021), in their research, reported 431.471 violence cases in Indonesia in 2019, which is an increase of about 6% from 2018, with a total of 406.178 (Noer et al., 2021). Other than that, in Indonesia, the inability to handle relationships could lead to a feeling of alienation. Alienation is an individual's separation from their environment. Apriyanti (2016) found in their research that the University of Indonesia's psychology students in Indonesia generally tended to show high levels of alienation. This indicated that the University of Indonesia's psychology students feel alienated from the learning process, the course, and their peers.

In regard to the importance of the ability to handle relationships among university students in Indonesia, it is important to understand the factors that relate to the ability of the students to handle relationships. One of the concepts related to the ability to handle relationships is emotional intelligence. According to Yu et al. (2006), emotional intelligence plays a significant role in handling interpersonal conflict. Going back to the traditional concept of emotional intelligence, one concept in emotional intelligence is non-intellective intelligence, which refers to individual affective and connective abilities, attitude, and behaviour (Khosravi et al., 2011). In this regard, connective abilities could foster positive relationships between students. Furthermore, Arakelian et al. (2013) stated that emotional intelligence is related to the ability to adapt to the environment, including humans. Research conducted by Pritamani (2021) revealed that there is a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and relationship satisfaction. It indicated that emotional intelligence helps students be able to manage and handle positive relationships with peers. Another study by Sadiku et al. (2019) revealed that improving emotional intelligence leads to stronger relationships. Based on several studies, it can be stated that the ability of students to handle relationships is associated with their emotional intelligence.

Emotional intelligence has certain factors, namely motivation, self-awareness, empathy, and managing emotion. Self-awareness includes metacognitive abilities such as the capacity to self-regulate and monitor performance, recognise performance errors, be aware of goals, and be able to find solutions and choose strategies (Sansone et al., 2021). Empathy is defined as an individual's cross-contextual tendency to emotionally share other people's feelings in their circumstances; empathy is also defined as an individual's cross-contextual tendency to imagine and understand other people's perspectives, mental circumstances, and feelings but without sharing their emotions (Donat et al., 2022). Managing emotion refers to the processes by which individuals manage the emotions they have, when they have them, and how they experience and express these emotions' (Lee et al., 2016). It is something related to individual experiences and expressions of emotion (Gross & John, 2003). Motivation refers to an internal condition that arouses, directs, and maintains behaviour (Woolfolk, 2013). Other than that, motivation is defined as a persuading feeling that always gives students optimism to complete a task or activity to the end and succeed in it, regardless of how difficult and challenging it is (Gopalan et al., 2017). In regard to the relation of emotional intelligence with handling relationships, this research intends to analyse the relation of a student's ability to handle relationships with several traits of emotional intelligence, namely motivation, self-awareness, empathy, and managing

emotion. The examination of the ability to handle relationships with certain factors of emotional intelligence is still sparse, and little empirical evidence is available in the Indonesian context. Therefore, this research will contribute to providing new insight regarding how Indonesian university students handle relationships.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The purpose of the current research was to investigate the influencing factors of handling relationships among university students in Indonesia. The current study's population consisted of university students in Indonesia. The information gathered via Google Forms is being disseminated to university students in Indonesia, including Palembang, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Kupang, Jogjakarta, and Jakarta. This study included 288 university students in total. Palembang had 12.8% of the participants, Nusa Tenggara Barat had 31.3% of the participants, Kupang had 49.7% of the people, Jogjakarta had 2.8% of the participants, and Jakarta had 3.5% of the participants. In terms of age, participants ranged from 17 to 26 years old, with the majority of participants being female (60.4%) and male (39.6%).

Instrument

Students handling relationships and the influencing factors were assessed through an instrument adopted from Arianti (2018). The instrument was adequately tested through factorial analysis, where each item of the construct was measured, namely handling relationships, managing emotions, self-awareness, empathy, and motivation for oneself, according to the construct. the factorial analysis result displayed in Table 1. Furthermore, the adequacy of the instrument was confirmed by the Cronbach alpha result. For the current data set, the result of the Cronbach alpha was 909.

Table 1: instrument validation

Dimension	Items	Communalities	Components					
			1	2	3	4	5	
Empathy	N19	.752	.860					
	N20	.734	.823					
	N21	.710	.786					
	N22	.733	.810					
	N24	.460	.630					
Handling Relationship	N26	.527		.607				
	N27	.465		.601				
	N28	.547		.643				
	N29	.631		.761				
	N30	.646		.728				
Motivation Oneself	N4	.647			.739			
	N11	.523			.634			
	N13	.603			.762			
	N15	.531			.548			
	N16	.568			.498			

	N25	.482			.465		
Self-awareness	N1	.479				.648	
	N3	.627				.724	
	N5	.577				.642	
	N6	.349				.378	
	N7	.636				.639	
	N9	.348				.380	
	N12	.589				.603	
Managing Emotion	N2	.402					.414
	N8	.461					.623
	N10	.404					.593
	N14	.647					.662
	N17	.336					.373
	N18	.450					.466
	N23	.460					.626

Procedure

This research is survey research. Researchers deploy the questionnaires to all respondents. Before the respondent fills out the questionnaire, the researcher states the purpose of data collection and how the data will be used. Researchers also explain the context of the research and the privacy of their data, saying that all data written in the research will be kept confidential and will only be used for research.

Next, we request their confirmation to voluntarily fill out the existing questionnaires by asking their willingness to fill out the Google form and answer with yes or no. This is to state that researchers do not press and require respondents to participate in this research. In addition, researchers only include data about their age and school location without including further details about their personal information.

Data analysis

The association among emotional intelligence traits, namely motivation, self-awareness, empathy, and managing emotion, with the ability to handle relationships was investigated through the estimation of the Pearson correlation and an a priori path analysis model. We hypothesised the influences of motivation on oneself to handle relationships fully mediated by self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy. Other than that, we hypothesised the direct correlation of self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy with handling relationships. A visual representation of the path analysis model is displayed in Figure 1.

In this model, motivation for oneself becomes the exogenous variable, handling relationships becomes the endogenous variable, and self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy become the intervening endogenous variables. The use of path analysis in this hypothesis is sufficient since path analysis is used to examine the correlational data to disentangle the causal processes underlying a particular outcome (Lleras, 2005). Path analysis can simply be used to test two or more causal models based on the researcher's hypothesis.

Figure 1: Hypothesis Model

RESULTS

Descriptive analysis and correlation analysis

Firstly, we examine the descriptive analysis of the dataset to review the skewness and kurtosis values in order to determine the normal distribution of the dataset. It is to determine if the data were approximately normally distributed, as certain latent variable modelling techniques are not robust to the incorporation of variables that violate the assumption of normality. The result of the skewness values for each factor was within the acceptable limit. However, the results of the kurtosis of motivation and handling relationships were higher than the threshold of -2 to +2, indicating the factors were not normally distributed. The result of the descriptive analysis can be further seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis

	Min	max	Std	kurtosis	skewness
Self-awareness	2.00	5.00	.54325	1.457	-.674
Managing emotion	2.14	5.00	.51099	1.024	-.592
Motivation oneself	1.50	5.00	.56291	2.027	-1.030
Handling relationship	1.60	5.00	.62686	2.147	-1.009
Empathy.	1.20	5.00	.74468	.078	-.197

The result of our correlation analysis revealed several interesting patterns. For instance, there was a significant correlation between the ability of the participants to handle relationships with self-awareness ($r = 0.490, p < 0.00$), managing emotion ($r = 0.429, p < 0.00$), and motivation ($r = 0.901, p < 0.00$). Other than that, there was a significant correlation between participants self-awareness with managing emotion ($r = 0.473, p < 0.00$), self-awareness with motivation (r

= 0.571, $p < 0.00$), and self-awareness with empathy ($r = 0.377$, $p < 0.00$). There is also a significant correlation between motivation oneself and managing emotion ($r = 0.410$, $p < 0.00$), empathy with managing emotion ($r = 0.350$, $p < 0.00$), empathy with motivation oneself ($r = 0.360$, $p < 0.00$), and empathy with their ability to handle relationships ($r = 0.435$, $p < 0.00$).

Table 3: Pearson Correlation

	1	2	3	4	5
(1) Self-awareness					
(2) Managing emotion	.473**				
(3) Motivation oneself	.571**	.410**			
(4) Handling relationship	.490**	.429**	.601**		
(5) Empathy	.377**	.350**	.360**	.435**	
	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Path analysis

In this research, path analysis was used to examine the predictive power of motivation for self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy, and the predictive power of self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy for the ability to handle relationships. Based on the result of the estimated regression weight, the model directly affected the variables, which were fitted with a significant value ($p < 0.05$). This is displayed in Table 4.

Table 4: Path Analysis

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
MEemotion	<---	Motiv_oneself	,372	,049	7,618	***	par_1
Empathy	<---	Motiv_oneself	,477	,073	6,543	***	par_2
SAwareness	<---	Motiv_oneself	,551	,047	11,787	***	par_6
hand_Relationship	<---	MEemotion	,242	,068	3,556	***	par_3
hand_Relationship	<---	SAwareness	,348	,065	5,372	***	par_4
hand_Relationship	<---	Empathy	,212	,045	4,769	***	par_5

Our review of standard part coefficient in figure 1 for the fully mediated a priori model indicated that the increase in the participants motivation on self was associated ($\beta = 0.55$, $p < 0.05$) with the increased participant self-awareness, was associated ($\beta = 0.37$, $p < 0.05$) with the increase of participants in managing emotion, and was associated ($\beta = 0.48$, $p < 0.05$) with the increased participant empathy. Our finding also indicated that the increased self-awareness of participants ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.05$) was associated with an increase in their ability to handle relationships. The increase in participant's ability to manage emotion was associated ($\beta = 0.24$, $p < 0.05$) with the increase in participant's ability to handle relationships. The increased participant empathy was associated ($\beta = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$) with the increased participant handling relationship.

Figure 2: Overview of Fully Mediated Path Model

Furthermore, the result indicated the indirect effect of participants motivation on themselves as much as .383 on the participants ability to handle relationships, as displayed in Table 5.

Table 5: Indirect Effect Path Analysis Model

	Motiv_oneself	SAwareness	Empathy	EMotion
SAwareness	,000	,000	,000	,000
Empathy	,000	,000	,000	,000
EMotion	,000	,000	,000	,000
hand_Relationship	,383	,000	,000	,000

DISCUSSION

The current research examines the correlation of several emotional intelligence traits to student handling relationships. Based on the finding, the Pearson correlation coefficient indicated a significant correlation between the ability of university students to handle relationships with their self-awareness, empathy, and emotion management. The significant correlation also confirms, through path analysis, that the p value for each correlation construct was significant. There was also a direct effect of self-awareness, motivation, and empathy towards handling relationships, and an indirect effect of motivation on handling relationships. In addition, researchers also examine the correlation between motivation and self-awareness, managing emotion, and empathy. This finding confirms the significant influences of several emotional intelligence traits on students ability to handle relationships. Morrison (2008), in their research, confirms the correlation between emotional intelligence traits and collaborating with others. They found that there is a positive correlation between the emotional intelligence trait and collaborating among the nurses sample. Akerjordet and Severinsson (2007) also conclude in

their research that emotional intelligence may have implications for the improvement of relationships and enhance the orientation towards positive values. Furthermore, among the university sample Arslan et al. (2010) conclude in their research that individuals with a high level of self-esteem (self-awareness) have a high level of life satisfaction, which is mediated by positive relationships with people around them. Other than that, they found that self-awareness could make individuals have the ability to solve social problems effectively and positively, which means that a high level of self-awareness has a positive correlation with dealing with confrontation or conflict.

Another construct measured in this research is the direct effect of empathy on handling relationships. In regard to empathy, Eisenberg et al. (2014) stated that empathy is known to be a positive social-emotional skill that is beneficial for social interaction and relationships. It is because empathy allows individuals to comprehend or share frames of reference with another person (Gunther et al., 2007). Therefore, Wink et al. (2021) in their research conclude that empathy is essential skill to manage behaviour and building positive relationship in the classroom. Other than that, Peck et al. (2015) stated that empathy is an underpinning factor of human relationship success. Anderson (2018) explains that it is important to develop individual empathy because it will make them able to feel what people around them are feeling. It will shape social understanding and begin to take others perspectives into account. Roberts (2017) stated that the effective relationship between humans is based on the understanding, attitude, and expectations of both parties. Therefore, in this case, empathy is essential for university students in building relationships with any stakeholder on their campus. It was confirmed in this research that path analysis shows the direct effect of empathy on handling relationships, and Pearson correlation confirms the significant relationship between empathy and handling relationships. This research also confirmed the direct effect of managing emotion on handling relationships among university students in Indonesia. Williams (2007) explained that the dimension of personal emotional management fosters trust and elevates effective cooperation between individuals. In an academic setting, both students and teachers suggested managing their own emotions to build resilience and relationships. Caruso et al. (2002) argue in their research that emotional management is an integral part of maintaining successful social interaction, including the interaction between students, teachers, and peers. It is even more important to emphasise the ability of university students to manage emotion because, at their age, they are facing emotional turmoil (Arnett, 2007). Thus, according to Rivers et al. (2013), it is salient to state that emotional management skills might help university students adjust to living in and outside their college. It is because they will be able to cope with their social interaction even when problems appear.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the current research was to examine the influence factor of handling relationships among university students in Indonesia. Using Pearson correlation, we identified a significant relationship between emotion management, empathy, self-awareness, and motivation to handling relationships. Furthermore, the proposed path model was found to be significant. Path analysis revealed a significant direct effect of self-awareness, empathy, and

emotion management on the handling relationship. We also identified a strong indirect influence of self-motivation on the handling relationship that was mediated by emotion management. The current study's findings, we believe, expand our understanding of the elements that influence university students' ability to manage their relationships.

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